

Metal Ion Oxidations in Solution. Part—III. The Oxidation of Benzyl Phenyl Glycollic Acids by Cerium (IV)

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The oxidation of Benzyl phenyl glycollic acid and the substituted ones by Ce(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid solutions has been studied at several temperatures. The oxidation of Benzyl phenyl glycollic acid is first order with respect to both Cerium(IV) and the organic substrate. The oxidation is found to be acid dependent. No indication for complex formation is observed. The effect of different substituents on the benzyl group of Benzyl phenyl glycollic acid (BPGA) has been evaluated.

Although the mechanism of oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids by Cerium(IV) is well established¹⁻³, systematic temperature dependence studies have not been made on these systems. No attempt till now has been made to study the effect of substituents on the rate of Ce(IV) oxidation and to examine the mechanistic approaches on the basis of the substituent effect.

The preparation of Cerium(IV) stock solutions and the experimental procedure were described previously⁴. Benzyl phenyl glycollic acid and the substituted ones were prepared from appropriately substituted chalcone epoxides and 2(N) alkali⁵. 3-Nitro chalcone epoxide was prepared by the method of Ballester and Bartlett⁶. Since the reaction was disturbed by atmospheric oxygen, the kinetics were followed in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Stock solution of the alpha-hydroxy acids were prepared in AnalaR Glacial Acetic Acid.

RESULTS

Stoichiometry and Product : Two moles of Cerium(IV) were found to be absorbed per mole of the BPGA. Carbon dioxide was evolved and upto 80% of the reaction desoxybenzoin was found to be the major product. However, with a large excess of cerium (IV) more than two moles of Ce(IV) were absorbed presumably due to further oxidation of desoxybenzoin and the work in that direction is still in progress.

Order of Reaction : Rate studies were made at different concentrations of the organic acid, oxidant and sulphuric acid. First order rate constants were derived graphically (Table-I).

Kinetics of Oxidation of Atrolactic acid by V(v) : *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 400 and by Ce(IV) : *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 239 may be considered as Part-I and II respectively.

1. A. McAuley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4054.
2. B. Krishna and K. C. Tewari, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3097.
3. P. Levesley and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.
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5. E. Rohrmann, R. G. Jones and H. A. Shonle, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1856.
6. M. Ballester and P. D. Bartlett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2042.

Acid Dependence : The reaction rate is dependent on the sulphuric acid concentration and the results of studies made at varying acid strengths at various temperatures are given in Table-I. Previous investigators¹⁷ in the oxidation of alpha-hydroxy acids have shown the rates to be inversely proportional to the square of sulphuric acid concentration; the retardation as pointed out by them, may presumably be due to the competition of the sulphate ion and the organic acid as ligands for Ce(IV). Plots of '*k*' against $1/[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ have been made at different temperatures. A linear relationship is seen at high concentrations but at higher *pH* values there is marked deviation. The temperature coefficient in different acid concentrations changes from 1.35 in 1*M* sulphuric acid to 2.04 in 2.5*M* sulphuric acid. This change in temperature coefficient may be ascribed to changes in redox potential of Ce(IV)/ Ce(III) from -1.61 in 1*N* sulphuric acid to -1.42 volts⁸ in 8*N* sulphuric acid.

TABLE I

Rate data for the Ce(IV) oxidation of Benzyl phenyl glycollic acid

Ce(IV) × 10 ³ in (M)	[BPGA] × 10 ³ in (M)	[H ₂ SO ₄] in (M)	<i>k</i> ₃₀ × 10 ⁴ in sec. ⁻¹	<i>k</i> ₃₅ × 10 ⁴ in sec. ⁻¹	$\frac{k_{30} \times 10^2 \text{ in lit.}}{[\text{BPGA}]}$ mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
3.71	5.0	2.0	11.34		
5.39	5.0	2.0	12.31		
10.00	5.0	2.0	11.61		
21.05	5.0	2.0	11.16		
26.95	5.0	2.0	11.57		
20.00	4.0	2.0	7.67		19.17
20.00	6.0	2.0	11.26		18.76
20.00	8.0	2.0	15.21		19.01
20.00	10.0	2.0	18.89	—	18.89
20.00	20.0	2.0	37.82	—	18.91
24.00	5.0	1.0	20.22	27.32	—
24.00	5.0	1.5	16.63	24.53	—
24.00	5.0	2.0	11.61	18.75	—
24.00	5.0	2.5	5.94	12.16	—

Energy-Entropy Relationship : The values of energy of activation, frequency factor have been calculated by employing Arrhenius equation and values of entropy of activation have been obtained from Eyring's equation. The trend in the energy of activation values do not follow the trend in reactivity. Entropy of activation values are positive and a correlated charge with energy of activation is observed. Therefore, a plot between E vs. ΔS^\ddagger is prepared and a straight line is obtained (except for the *p*-methoxy group). Therefore, the

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8. Oxidation in Organic Chemistry, Ed. by K. B. Wiberg, Academic Press, 1965, p. 245.

reaction follows compensation law of Leffler⁹, $\Delta H^\ddagger(E) = \Delta H_0^\ddagger(E_0) + \beta\Delta S^\ddagger$, and so the same mechanistic path is followed by all substituted compound (except of course *p*-methoxy compound). The values of β , the isokinetic temperature and $\Delta H_0^\ddagger(E_0)$ have been found to be 319°K and 17.67 Kcals/mole respectively. The positive entropy of activation values indicate a less crowded transition state.

Effect of Substituents on the Benzyl group : The results for the oxidation of substituted acids are given in Table-II. The order of reactivity of different substituents is *o*-Cl > 2,4-dichloro > *m*-nitro > hydrogen > *p*-methyl > *p*-methoxy. In general the electron withdrawing substituents accelerate and the electron donating ones retard the rate.

TABLE II

Rate data at various temperatures, Arrhenius parameters and entropy of activation values for the Ce(IV) oxidation of substituted benzyl phenyl glycollic acids

$$[\text{Ce(IV)}] \times 10^3 = 6.473(M); [\text{Hydroxy Acid}] \times 10^3 = 10.0(M); [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0M$$

Name of the substituent	$k \times 10^3$ in lit. mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹							E in Kcals/mole	log PZ	ΔS^\ddagger
	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	50°	55°			
<i>o</i> -Cl	24.18*	58.05	116.10	185.00	—	—	—	21.56	15.46	12.21
2,4-Cl ₂	21.77	38.09	87.08	161.70	—	—	—	24.16	17.23	20.36
3-NO ₂	11.79	28.65	81.62	130.60	—	—	—	31.18	22.01	42.38
H	—	24.45	39.69	87.18	178.60	—	—	23.25	16.33	16.21
4-CH ₃	7.29	15.05	25.70	85.06	—	—	—	31.80	22.34	43.90
4-OHC ₃	—	—	—	0.22	0.41	1.21	2.18	22.74	13.37	2.58

* Not included in the calculation of E .

Mechanism : In view of the above considerations and in the light of the observations by Waters *et al.*⁴ the following reaction scheme can be formulated :

The first step involves a complex formation. To examine if a complex is formed, the reaction was studied at different concentrations of the organic substrate and rate data (Table-1) have been fitted to the equation suggested by Duke¹⁰.

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{k_2} + \frac{1}{Kk_2} \cdot \frac{1}{[\text{OS}]}$$

9. J. E. Leffler, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, **20**, 1202.

10. F. R. Duke and A. A. Forrist, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2790.

A linear plot between $1/k$ and $1/[\text{OS}]$ passing through the origin has been obtained which suggests that a complex may not be formed. A complex formation has been proposed for the Ce(IV) oxidation of atrolactic acid⁴ in which electron donating ability of the methyl group and electron withdrawing nature of the phenyl group may have a compensating effect. Since the complex formation is precluded the O-H or C-H bond rupture giving rise to a free radical appears probable. That a free radical is formed is indicated by the induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The two alternate mechanisms (I and II) may, hence be proposed.

Mechanism-I :

Mechanism-II :

Both the mechanisms explain the formation of the product and the rate expression. But Mechanism-II looks more elegant owing to the large substituent effect observed. Moreover, there is lot of crowding around the CH₂- group and in forming the free radical intermediate, this strain can be released which explains also the positive entropy of activation values. Mechanism-I on the other hand cannot possibly explain the positive ΔS^\ddagger values. The carbon carbon bond breaks due to the presence exerted by the bulky groups. This is supported by (i) the greater rate of oxidation of benzyl phenyl glycollic acid than atro-lactic

acid, (ii) the ortho-effect of chlorine atom in ortho chloro and 2,4-dichloro benzyl phenyl glycollic acid. This is also in analogy to the rate of oxidation of pinacol and butane-2,3-diol.¹¹

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